

Anomalous US-wide prevalence of reversion mutants in the emergence of Omicron BA.1

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Abstract

Surface glycoprotein sequences of the Omicron BA.1 lineage that include only reverse mutations were searched in NCBI GenBank, where the dates and the locations of collection were retrieved for each mutant. Data from BA.1.x lineages that appeared during the same period of time were used as a control, and the early spread of these mutants were compared. The number of states where the first 20 samples were found was compared between the group of reversion mutants and the control group. The result shows that the reversion mutants were widespread from the early days of their emergence, which shows statistically significant differences compared to the control group. Whether the origin of a mutant is natural infection from abroad, domestic natural mutation, or leakage from a laboratory, it is usually possible to make a rough estimation of the epicenter by tracing its spread. The wide prevalence of reversion mutants of BA.1 from the beginning of their emergence is highly anomalous and extremely unlikely to occur without human intervention.

Keywords

SARS-CoV-2, Omicron variant, reverse mutation, epidemiology, infection spread

Introduction

Many researchers have suspected that the original strain of SARS-CoV-2 might have leaked from the Wuhan Institute of Virology (WIV) [1-8]. Though some virologists claimed SARS-CoV-2 had originated in the Huanan Seafood Market based on early mutations and sampling locations at the onset of the outbreak [9,10], allegation of sampling bias was made against them in the following publications [11,12]. On June 20, 2023, the Wall Street Journal reported the names of three researchers in the WIV who fell sick with typical symptoms of COVID-19 in November 2019 [13]. According to the article, US investigators had confirmed that these researchers were working with the viruses close to SARS-CoV-2, occasionally manipulating the genomic sequence.

On January 18, 2024, the U.S. Right to Know released an early draft of research grant proposal called “DEFUSE” obtained through the Freedom of Information Act (FOIA) [14], where a detailed blueprint to synthesize a SARS-CoV-2-like virus, which had been predicted by a previous study [15], was included. Some scientists evaluated this document as a smoking gun of the lab-leak hypothesis, while a group of virologists promoting gain-of-function research strongly opposed this view.

On the other hand, the origins of SARS-CoV-2 variants have not been discussed as vigorously as that of the original Wuhan strain. Among the major variants of concerns (VOCs) of SARS-CoV-2, the Omicron variant, which includes 30 or more non-synonymous (N) mutations and only one synonymous (S) mutation in the surface glycoprotein (spike protein) [16], is significantly different from the VOCs that had only around 10 spike mutations. Phylogenetic analysis shows that the Omicron variant did not emerge from the other precedent VOCs [17]. It is also noteworthy that most mutations among these VOCs are independent from

each other. Hassan et al. surveyed mutations in various VOCs across the continents to find that many mutations were specific to each location [18], which could have caused the emergence of independent mutations.

Tanaka and Miyazawa have found that the data of the Omicron variants BA.1, BA.1.1, and BA.2 registered in NCBI (National Center for Biotechnology Information) GenBank comprise sequences with a single reverse mutation and no other mutations in the spike protein [19], indicating a trace of reversion experiments to see the effect of each mutation. Kakeya and Matsumoto have found reversions in D614G of the spike proteins in the Delta variant (B.1.617.2) and the Omicron variant BA.2 in the late stage of their community spread [20].

Following these studies, Kakeya and Kanazaki compared the histograms of mutations in the spike proteins of major variants, where BA.1 is outstanding in its high reverse mutation rate and low variety of mutations [21]. Among the reverse mutations of Omicron BA.1, H681P reversion while preserving K679 is least likely to emerge naturally either through homologous recombination, point mutation, or both of them put together when the sequence alignment and mutation spectrum are taken into account.

Before the paper by Tanaka and Miyazawa, popular explanations on the origin of the Omicron variant were either unknown human population under strong selective pressure to escape from vaccine-induced immune response, incubation in an immunocompromised patient, or evolution in a non-human host before spilling over back to human [22]. However, highly vaccinated populations in developed countries are well-monitored by the health administration, meaning that emergence of many mutations in the community spread without being noticed is practically impossible. As for incubation in an immunocompromised patient, the count of

mutations observed so far is around 10 or fewer [23-25], which is not comparable to that observed in the Omicron variant.

The dN/dS ratio, which compares N mutations to S mutations, is often used to measure selective pressure [26,27]. Though high dN/dS ratios are consistent in all the VOCs [28], the amount of mutations in the Omicron variants stands out. Wei et al. argue that dN/dS as high as 6.64, which is observed in the spike protein of the Omicron variant, is extremely unlikely to emerge in an immunocompromised patient [29]. Mutation of virus can have a dN/dS value much higher than unity only when the virus spreads among multiple species [30]. However, even the HIV-1 regulatory gene *tat*, which is known for its high selective pressure, has around 1.5 dN/dS ratio in the human population [31]. In SARS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2, dN/dS is usually smaller than unity [32].

Wei et al. indicated that the Omicron variant had evolved in mice [29], which was followed by Zhang et al. [33]. It is known, however, that the original strain of SARS-CoV-2 does not infect mice [34]. Kakeya et al. claimed that a lab origin of the Omicron variant is likely [35], possibly caused by a spill-over from transgenic mice [36], which preceded the discovery by Tanaka and Miyazawa that the sequence data of Omicron variant BA.1, BA1.1, and BA.2 comprise footprints of reverse genetics experiments.

Though a consensus on the origin of the Omicron variant is not still reached, the discovery by Tanaka and Miyazawa is worth being studied further. In this paper, we investigate how the Omicron BA.1 including reverse mutations spread in its emergence and compare it with the spread of other Omicron lineages in the same period of time.

Methods

The surface glycoprotein (spike protein) data of Omicron BA.1 were downloaded from NCBI GenBank in June 2023. To save computational cost, protein sequences including deletion and insertion with respect to the consensus BA.1 sequence were removed from the analyses.

It is reported that the sequences of the Omicron variant sampled in the early stage of its surge were contaminated with those of the Delta variant due to primer issues, which gave massive appearance of reverse mutations [37]. To see the extent of contamination, the sequences without missing reads and mutations included in the Delta variant are examined.

The surface glycoprotein sequences of BA.1 including only reverse mutations (pure reversion mutants) were searched in GenBank, where the dates and the locations of collection were retrieved for each mutant. Data with missing reads were included for analysis except for those including missing reads at the mutation points of the Omicron BA.1, where missing amino acids were assumed to be the same as those of the consensus sequence. The date and location data of BA.1 derivatives with more than 60 and fewer than 820 registered surface glycoprotein sequences (BA.1.1.4, BA.1.1.6, BA.1.1.7, BA.1.1.8, BA.1.1.10, BA.1.1.11, BA.1.1.13, BA.1.1.15, BA.1.1.16, BA.1.1.17, BA.1.4, BA.1.5, BA.1.6, BA.1.13, BA.1.14, BA.1.14.1, BA.1.15.1, BA.1.15.3, BA.1.16, BA.1.19, BA.1.21) were also downloaded from GenBank for comparison.

Data sampled in the United States with their collection dates and locations (names of the states) registered were analyzed, where the number of the states in which the first 20 samples were detected for each group

was counted and compared. When the date of collection was the same, data registered earlier were counted as earlier samples. Statistical tests were given between the reversion group and the control group, where the criteria to be included in each group were adjusted in multiple ways to avoid sampling bias. Change over time of the amount and location (state) of collection was plotted and mapped for each group.

Results

The histogram of spike mutations for the BA.1 sequences comprising neither missing reads nor mutations specific to Delta variant are compared with that for all the BA.1 sequences in Figures 1-A and 1-B, where sequences with insertion or deletion are excluded in both groups. Figures 1-C and 1-D focus on the positions of point mutations from the original Wuhan strain to the Omicron BA.1, where no conspicuous difference is observed except for amino acids 477, 478, 484, 796, and 981 in spikes.

Pure reversion mutants that have 20 or more registered data including dates and locations (states in the United States) of collection are listed in Table 1, which comprises the total number of entries with collection dates and locations (NECDL), the date of first collection, the number of days before reaching 10 samples of collection (NDBR10), and the number of states where the first 20 samples were found (NSF20). The same set of data for the control group are listed in Table 2. Correlations between the parameters listed in Tables 1 and 2 are shown in Figure 2, where weak correlations are found between NECDL and NSF20 (negative correlation) as well as between NDBR10 and NSF20 (positive correlation) in the control group.

To investigate whether a statistically significant difference is found in the NSF20 between the group of pure

reversion mutants and the control group, t-test assuming unequal variance was performed by changing the constituents of each group using various criteria of data entry with respect to NECDL and NDBR10. Based on the result given by Figure 1, a comparison excluding less reliable reversion mutants (those comprising reversions at 477, 478, 484, 796, and 981) was also performed. Means and standard deviations (SDs) of NSF20s in each group as well as the results of t-tests assuming unequal variance are shown in Table 3. As the table shows, the NSF20s in the pure reversion mutants are larger than those in the control group with significant difference, where two-tail p values are all in the order of 10^{-4} or smaller, meaning that the reversion mutants were notably widespread from the beginning of their emergence.

Figure 3 shows the histograms of collection dates and the maps of the United States illustrating the spread of BA.1 reversion mutants, while Figure 4 shows those illustrating the spread of close lineages in the control group (reversion mutants and lineages comprising more than 50 samples and with NDBR10 equal to 21 or smaller are shown). Wide prevalence of reversion mutants across the United States is conspicuous from the beginning of their emergence except for the 417-th amino acid reversion, while the lineages in the control group have visible epicenters from which infection spread.

Discussion

The results of the analyses show that the pure reversion mutants were prevalent across the United States from the beginning of their emergence. Whether the origin of each mutant is natural infection from abroad, domestic natural mutation, or leakage from a laboratory, its epicenter is usually traceable. As for major variants, Alpha variants (B.1.1.7) were mainly found in California and Florida, while Delta variants were

heavily collected in California in the early days of the spread in the United States. Kakeya and Matsumoto investigated the epicenter of G614D reverse mutation, which is not expected to emerge through natural infection and is suspected to have a lab origin, to find the epicenter of G614D reversion in the Delta variant around the Great Lakes and that in the Omicron BA.2 variant along the downstream of the Hudson River [20].

From this point of view, the spread of reversion mutants across the United States from the beginning of their emergence is extremely abnormal. The effect of data contamination, which has already been discussed above, is further denied by the fact that the mutants that have reversions at 417 in spike has a clear epicenter of infection. If the reads of reversion mutants include contamination of preceding variants in general, the reversion at 417 also has to be found all around the United States from the beginning.

Since the sequences of the reversion mutants and those in the control group were found in the same period of time and are genetically close to each other, the difference cannot be attributed to seasonal or epidemiologically specific factors. It is also noteworthy that the pure reversion mutants disappeared soon, which means that they are not competitive against the other Omicron BA.1 mutants enough to spread widely in the early days of their emergence through natural infections. If we do not consider possibilities of any super-natural phenomena, the only explanation that can account for this anomalous spread of pure reversion mutants is an unidentified human intervention to accelerate wide infections.

It is known that there are substantially no oversights of research activities in the field of virology. Therefore, it is easy to carry out risky research that can cause immense damage to the health of a large population

covertly in a small facility. In 2023, Chinese researchers were found to be keeping nearly 1000 mice for experiments and samples of at least 20 potentially infectious agents including malaria, dengue fever, and SARS-CoV-2 in a secretive research facility in the city of Reedley, California [38].

Though it is of urgent importance to strengthen the oversight of research activities in virology [39], it is hard to trace all research activities, including those performed covertly. In addition to the oversight by health officials, patrol by police department and espionage by intelligence agencies are needed. Litigation outlawing any unreported virology research activities and imposing heavy criminal punishment on its violators can also be a strong deterrence to creating and spreading pathogenic viruses.

Conflicts of interest

The author declares no conflict of interests exist.

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Table 1. List of pure reversion mutants comprising the number of states where the first 20 samples were found (NSF20), the number of samples with registered dates and locations (name of state) of collection, the date of first sample collection, and the number of days before reaching 10 samples of collection (NDBR10). Reversions at 440-446, which comprise only 19 data, are also listed for reference, where NSF20 is replaced with NFS19.

Reversion at	417	440	446	547	856	981	339-375
NSF20	4	9	12	13	16	18	13
NECDL	279	37	20	35	30	20	23
Date of first collection	Nov-26	Dec-14	Dec-19	Dec-20	Dec-9	Dec-10	Dec-8
NDBR10	11	13	28	3	21	17	20
Reversion at	417-446	417-446, 764	417, 477-505	417-505	477-505	493-505	440-446
NSF20	12	12	16	15	10	12	14
NECDL	250	52	114	63	80	95	19
Date of first collection	Dec-9	Dec-16	Dec-13	Dec-14	Dec-13	Dec-4	Dec-1
NDBR10	5	6	2	4	4	10	26

Table 2 List of 21 BA.1 derivatives with more than 60 and fewer than 820 registered surface glycoprotein sequences in GenBank, accompanied by the number of states where the first 20 samples were found (NSF20), the number of entries with collection dates and locations (NECDL), the date of first sample collection, and the number of days before reaching 10 samples of collection (NDBR10).

Lineage	BA.1.1.4	BA.1.1.6	BA.1.1.7	BA.1.1.8	BA.1.1.10	BA.1.1.11	BA.1.1.13
NSF20	3	4	13	3	8	11	12
NECDL	31	47	75	734	507	50	42
First collection date	Dec-26	Dec-10	Dec-13	Nov-26	Dec-2	Dec-22	Dec 14
NDBR10	11	12	23	17	21	54	36
Lineage	BA.1.1.15	BA.1.1.16	BA.1.1.17	BA.1.4	BA.1.5	BA.1.6	BA.1.13
NSF20	9	6	4	5	11	9	10
NECDL	73	611	299	31	35	49	113
First collection date	Dec-9	Dec-2	Dec-14	Dec-13	Dec-16	Dec-22	Nov-29
NDBR10	14	17	9	22	24	7	15
Lineage	BA.1.14	BA.1.14.1	BA.1.15.1	BA.1.15.3	BA.1.16	BA.1.19	BA.1.21
NSF20	4	3	7	11	8	7	9
NECDL	245	97	598	23	47	693	102
First collection date	Dec-10	Dec-20	Dec-6	Dec-22	Dec-13	Dec-3	Dec-4
NDBR10	6	10	6	31	16	10	21

Table 3. Data counts, means, and standard deviations (SDs) of NSF20s in the reversion mutant group and the control group, accompanied by the results of two-tail t-tests assuming unequal variance. In addition to statistical analysis using all data, data sets satisfying $NECDL \leq 250$, $NDBR10 \leq 21$ (three weeks), $NDBR10 \leq 21$ & $NECDL \leq 250$, and $NDBR10 \leq 21$ & $NECDL \leq 250$ excluding reversions at 477, 478, 484, 796, or 981 were tested to mitigate bias and to enhance data reliability.

	Reversions			Control			t- test
	# Data	Mean	SD	# Data	Mean	SD	<i>p</i> value
All Data	13	12.5	3.6	21	7.5	3.2	4.1×10^{-4}
$NECDL \leq 250$	12	13.2	2.6	15	8.1	3.4	2.2×10^{-4}
$NDBR10 \leq 21$	12	12.5	3.7	15	6.3	2.5	9.1×10^{-5}
$NDBR10 \leq 21, NECDL \leq 250$	11	13.3	2.7	9	6.6	3.0	6.0×10^{-5}
Reliable, $NDBR10 \leq 21, NECDL \leq 250$	7	12.4	2.1	9	6.6	3.0	3.7×10^{-4}

Figure 1-A

Figure 1-B

Figure 1-C

Figure 1-D

Figure 1. (A) The histogram of spike mutations for all the BA.1 sequences with neither insertion nor deletion registered in GenBank (total data size is 49715), (B) that for the BA.1 sequences comprising neither insertion, deletion, missing reads, nor mutations specific to Delta variant (total data size is 22141), and those focusing the amino acids of the Omicron BA.1 different from the original Wuhan strain, where (C) comprises all the BA.1 sequences registered and (D) comprises neither missing reads nor mutations specific to Delta variant.

A

B

Figure 2. (A) The correlation between the number of samples (NECDL) and the number of states where the first 20 samples were found (NSF20). (B) The correlation between the number of days before reaching 10 samples of collection (NDBR10) and NSF20.

Figure 3-A: reversion at 417

A-0

A-1

A-2

A-3

A-4

Figure 3-B: reversions at 417-446

B-0

B-1

B-2

Figure 3-C: reversions at 417-446, 764

C-0

C-1

C-2

Figure 3-D: reversions at 417, 477-505

D-0

D-1

D-2

Figure 3-E: reversions at 417-505

E-0

E-1

E-2

Figure 3-F: reversions at 477-505

F-0

F-1

F-2

F-4

Figure 3-G: reversions at 493-505

G-0

G-1

G-2

G-3

Figure 3. Histograms of collection dates (X-0) and maps of the United States illustrating the spread of BA.1 reversion mutants (X-1, X-2, X-3, X-4). X-N shows the collection counts in each US state during the N-th phase of spread, each of which is marked with different colors in X-0.

Figure 4-A: BA.1.1.8

A-0

A-1

A-2

A-3

A-4

Figure 4-B: BA.1.1.10

B-0

B-1

B-2

B-3

B-4

Figure 4-C: BA.1.1.15

C-0

C-1

C-2

C-3

C-4

Figure 4-D: BA.1.1.16

D-0

D-1

D-2

D-3

D-4

Figure 4-E: BA.1.1.17

E-0

E-1

E-2

E-3

E-4

Figure 4-F: BA.1.13

F-0

F-1

F-2

F-3

F-4

Figure 4-G: BA.1.14

G-0

G-1

G-2

G-3

G-4

Figure 4-H: BA.1.14.1

H-0

H-1

H-2

H-3

H-4

Figure 4-I: BA.1.15.1

I-0

I-1

I-2

I-3

I-4

Figure 4-J: BA.1.19

J-0

J-1

J-2

J-3

J-4

Figure 4-K: BA.1.21

K-0

K-1

K-2

K-3

K-4

Figure 4. Histograms of collection dates (X-0) and maps of the United States illustrating the spread of BA.1 derivatives (X-1, X-2, X-3, X-4). X-N shows the collection counts in each US state during the N-th phase of spread, each of which is marked with different colors in X-0.